

Driving impact through responsible investing

Opportunities for business and business schools

20th ABIS Annual Colloquium
23 November 2021

On 23 November 2021 ABIS convened its 20th Annual Colloquium during which speakers and participants engaged in keynote speeches, panel discussions, research presentations and interactive sessions on the timely topic of "Driving responsible investing to deliver impact".

The conference created a dialogue between practitioners and academics centering on the question: **how to enhance positive business impact on society through responsible investing?** In particular, speakers and participants addressed the related benefits and **opportunities for business and business schools.**

Audience

The conference welcomed responsible investing professionals, business practitioners, as well as scholars and educators in business, management and sustainable finance. The event was an opportunity for them to engage with each other, learn and discuss the latest insights and developments in responsible investing. We were pleased to:

- have **75 registrations**
- from which we welcomed **40 participants** at the live event!
- representing around **30 organizations...** and **10 countries!**

If you have missed the event, you can now find the **session summaries, recordings** and **resources for further learning** in the following pages.

Keynote speech: "Investing for a sustainable future"

After a welcome speech by **Karolina Sobczak**, Knowledge Manager at ABIS, **Adrie Heinsbroek**, Chief Sustainability Officer at NN Investment Partners started off with a reflection on **investing as preparing for the future**. In essence, responsible investors assess the strategic decision-making by companies and government and choose to invest the capital entrusted to them in those actions that contribute to the future. **Investors' capital allocation is driven by the capital allocation of the investee companies and governments** (new double materiality) – and it is not only about financial capital. Investors need to assess the outlook for value creation in an integrated way. In doing this, dialogue with companies and governments is essential as well as taking an active role.

Finance in general is called to change from just shifting capital in financial transactions to impact in the real economy e.g. not just reducing carbon of portfolios (simply divesting), but also allocating capital to make the transition to a low-carbon economy happen. It is balancing act though: investors need to respond to stakeholder expectations, but also to adapt to new realities and make sure to provide a certain return. **Shareholders have the responsibility to take action on issues that matter to stakeholders**, because investing is for the benefit of the future society. The interconnection of interests is what counts and creates new value.

Responsible investors are change agents, or at least they can and should be!

Business education has a big opportunity in this shift by nurturing and developing:

- new mindset
- open mindedness
- awareness of the broader contexts and of the complexity of stakeholder interests and expectations
- the value in sharing experiences and knowledge
- willingness to try out different solutions with others
- learning from real world examples
- insights and modelling

Future professionals and leaders need to be able to link sustainability to business drivers and societal value creation. Academia needs to look at what works, what can be improved and what needs to be taken into consideration.

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Panel discussion: "Investors and banks as changemakers - making it work"

- **Hans Biemans** - Head of Sustainable Markets, Managing Director, ING
- **Nancy Kamp-Roelands** - Professor of Non-financial information, Integrated Reporting and Assurance, University of Groningen
- **Carol Tarr** – Portfolio Manager, Kavedon Kapital
- **Maarten Vleeschhouwer** - Head of PACTA, 2° Investing Initiative
- Moderator: **Ivo Matser** - Chief Executive Officer, ABIS

The session featured a number of relevant voices in the finance sector, who shared their approaches on responsible investing. **Carol Tarr** explained how at **Kavedon Kapital, a VC built on circular economy principles**, they go beyond the financial issues to also focus on how founders are treated and on the circularity of social capital and knowledge, which build more resilient businesses and long-term returns for all stakeholders. **Hans Biemans** shared how ING is steering its loan portfolio towards zero carbon, as well as its bonds and financial services to help businesses adopt sustainable practices. He perceives an **increase in awareness about sustainability, missing in communication** – investors do not invest in entire supply chains in a conscious way yet, financing the whole transition.

With her integrated reporting lens, **Nancy Kamp-Roelands** called for a change in financial and non-financial reporting. For this, new competences are needed. Business schools can play a huge role by promoting shared value for business and stakeholders, integrated thinking, linking long term societal challenges to business opportunities.

We need professionals in businesses with new knowledge about investing, but we also need to teach investors to ask companies for sustainability results.

Maarten Vleeschhouwer shared the role of 2°II in connecting financial portfolios and climate goals. 2°II developed PACTA, an open-source portfolio alignment methodology that can be used freely by investors and banks to assess their portfolios and loans against the Paris Agreement goals. The approach taken is sectoral: certain sectors will need to decarbonize faster than others due to technologies available (e.g. automotive vs steel), while others will need to disappear (fossil fuels). PACTA compares sectoral decarbonization pathways based on scenarios and benchmarks the performance of investee companies.

The discussion then centered around the **incentives needed** to support and accelerate sustainable investing. A series of interesting perspectives were brought up. One approach suggested to **focus on wellbeing and non-financial indicators** to drive financial performance. Developing a **long-term focus on societal needs** rather than short-term demand and returns will be important. Besides incentives to finance environmentally friendly investments such as the **Green Supporting Factor** or **tax incentive instruments** (e.g. the Dutch Green Funds Scheme), **transparency** will be a much more effective driver. With the EU Taxonomy focusing on activities (i.e. product rather than corporate level), what is going to help are **new datasets, machine-readable sustainability information**, as well as sound **classification systems** – with a great opportunity for academics to play a role.

The increasing awareness around the **strong business case** in the sustainability transition per se is also going to drive investment in the area and a further push is going to come from the **regulatory and supervisory bodies**. While some organizations do a lot, there is also a lot of storytelling, but the current action is not deep enough.

Harmonization in reporting is also necessary and the new EU CSRD is going in the right direction.

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Company perspectives and opportunities

The next session featured cases which exemplify ways in which business can integrate, benefit from and create positive impact by adopting responsible investing principles and strategies.

Case 1. Managing sustainability reporting and circular transformation

- **Iris van Wanrooij** - Program Manager Corporate Social Responsibility, Emma Safety Footwear

Iris van Wanrooij started with a brief overview of [Latour](#), a Swedish investment company owning [Hultafors Group](#), by which [EMMA Safety Footwear](#) was recently acquired. Latour takes a long-term investing approach, with 64% of value coming from holdings owned for over 20 years and with increasing stakes in sustainability-focused companies.

The EMMA brand has been a perfect addition to their portfolio, due to its history as **one of the first Dutch social enterprises**. EMMA started a **journey into circular economy** in 2015 to address resource scarcity concerns and improve its supply chain. Iris showcased how EMMA was able to **maximize the use of recycled materials** especially of polyurethane production waste, to **increase the use water-based adhesives**, to **recycle wastewater and leather waste** and to **improve labour conditions in their supply chain**. In order to generate scale in the volume of recycled shoes and drive costs down, EMMA formed the [Circular Footwear Alliance](#) (CFA) together with other actors in the Dutch footwear industry. EMMA reports to its mother company on its sustainability performance each quarter through the Worldfavor platform and publishes regular sustainability reports. The main learnings in their journey revolve around the need to **think long term**, the importance of data to **accumulate knowledge on the supply chain to identify points of improvement**, keeping eyes open and **cooperating with partners** within the supply chain. Finally, they also suggest to focus beyond carbon reduction and more on social aspects, circularity, and material loops.

2021: use of 85% water-based adhesives and a water-based release agent

Yearly Consumption Electricity, Gas, Water

Year	Electricity (kWh)	Gas (m ³)	Water (m ³)
2018	~100,000	~100,000	~100,000
2019	~100,000	~100,000	~100,000
2020	~100,000	~100,000	~100,000
2021	~100,000	~100,000	~100,000

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Case 2. Creating social impact through innovative financing approaches

- **Roberta Bosurgi** - CEO, European Venture Philanthropy Association

[EVPA](#) is a network of 3.000 members including capital providers, corporate foundations, capacity building organizations, accelerators, incubators etc. They are motivated by the vision that deployment of resources should not be a binary mechanism for only financial return. They **link Venture Philanthropy with the concept of Investing for Impact**, characterized by a long-term and high-engagement approach and consisting of three core practices:

- Tailored Financing (e.g. grants, loans, equity)
- Non-financial support (capacity building)
- Impact Measurement and Management

These allow investors to invest in social enterprises, combining market returns with social impact. Roberta argued that **all kinds of capital have a role to play** and investors can get involved based on risk tolerance and attitude on impact. EVPA identifies different forms of financial instruments (grants, debts, equity, hybrid financial investments) with a **“patient” approach** and non-financial support. Impact measurement is crucial for transparency and accountability, but also helps to adjust business models according to the impact aimed to be delivered. Corporate social investors can contribute to different challenges, through corporate foundations, impact accelerators, corporate social businesses, and impact funds. Through these tools, companies can enhance their impact and avoid bad practices and greenwashing. **Setting up the right corporate impact vehicles** helps to overcome legal restrictions, unlocking extra financial instruments to support social entrepreneurs. For example, Rabobank supported the development of new sustainable technologies and new materials in Dutch rural areas through the [Rabo Rural Fund](#). Schneider Electric set up its [Energy Access Fund](#) to make capital available for innovative startups with affordable green energy solutions accessible to low-income population.

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Latest research findings

After lunch, we proceeded to learn about the latest research findings on responsible investing and sustainable finance both from academic and practitioner presentations.

Track 1: ESG, Corporate Governance and Value Creation

- Chair: **Joan Fontrodona** - Professor and Director of Business Ethics Department, IESE Business School
- **Habeeb Bolaji Yahya**, Turku School of Economics: *Firm Environmental, Social, and Governance Performance: the relevance to profitability and value*
- **Adrie Heinsbroek & Florentine van den Eerenbeemt**, NN Investment Partners & Glass Lewis: *Exploring the links between ESG supervision and performance*
- **Rashed Hasan**, George Mason University: *Stakeholder Value Index: A Holistic Approach to Purpose, People, Planet and Prosperity*
- **Rodrigo Kambayashi**, IESEG School of Management: *Investigating the relationship on UNGC membership and ESG performance*
- **Irina Bakhtina & Yury Blagov**, GSoM St. Petersburg University: *Green Products and ESG Engagement Strategies*

[RECORDING Research Findings Track 1: ESG, Corporate Governance and Value Creation](#)

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The Academy of Business in Society

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Selling a 'Green Product' as an ESG Engagement Strategy

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Graduate School of Management
St. Petersburg University

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Track 2: Responsible Investing approaches and performance

- Chair: **Luk Van Wassenhove** - Emeritus Professor of Technology and Operations Management, INSEAD
- **Isobel Edwards**, NN Investment Partners: *Top-down versus bottom-up investing in green bond funds: a case study review*
- **Davide Bonomi**, ESMT Berlin: *ESG investment performance compared to non-ESG*
- **Quintin Rayer**, Coventry University & P1 Investment Management Ltd: *Towards a definition of Ethical Investment*
- **Lee-Ann Steenkamp & Suzette Viviers**, Stellenbosch University: *Shareholder-initiated environmental and energy resolutions: Too little too late?*
- **Joel Diener**, Catholic University of Eichstaett-Ingolstadt: *Assessing strategies and tools of Christian-Influenced SRI funds*

[RECORDING Research Findings Track 2: Responsible Investing approaches and performance](#)

The research presented in this session will be published in a related issue of the **Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal**. The call for papers is still open for further papers and is available at [this link](#). The **deadline for submission** of full papers is **31 January 2022**.

Fishbowl discussion: "Responsible Investing and sustainability education – are business schools missing out?"

Opening statements by:

- **Jörg Rocholl** - President, ESMT Berlin
- **Tim Mescon** - Executive Vice President and Chief Officer, EMEA, AACSB

Last but not least, this interactive session reflected on what is the reality of responsible investing education in business school and how business schools can educate leaders with a **more integrated understanding of sustainable decisions-making**.

Jörg Rocholl suggested five postulates for business schools. What is needed is **(1) substance/ evidence** for business of actual green transformation rather than marketing, **(2) coherence** and **(3) comprehensiveness** in embedding sustainability in programs or research, but also in more visible ways (e.g. how business school buildings can be CO2 neutral), **(4) an interdisciplinary approach** to understand what scientists need from business schools (and companies), but also what business schools need from climate scientists, and **(5) grassroot initiatives** bringing up a sense of urgency and community and in which everyone can contribute. A great example are the [Sustainability Ambassadors at ESMT Berlin](#), who have been tracking the carbon footprint of ESMT Berlin through a carbon accounting software.

Tim Mescon highlighted the shift that is happening in the “hottest” MBA programs, from topics like mergers and acquisitions and game theory to **climate finance, social justice, impact investing, social entrepreneurship** – professionals whose positions would traditionally do not include sustainability will be equipped with knowledge on sustainability. As McKinsey reports, sustainable investing globally mobilized a lot of money, creating growth in sustainable business cases and related jobs. There is a need for graduates who understand SDGs, climate risks, renewable energy and able to make recommendations on sustainable investments - 70% of finance roles are newly created because the rapidly growing sustainability is a sector that will grow rapidly, and the context is different of what it was a decade ago. Therefore, there is a **surging need for sustainability literacy and education** and courses around the world are increasing.

A lively discussion among other participants followed. The point of **bringing theory and practice together** on the sustainability transformation emerged. While challenging, there is a need for practitioners from business and academics to learn from each other, to create inspiration and show how knowledge from business schools can be applied in practice. Sustainable decision-making is also going to be driven by **societal pressures**, the demand from students, consumers and the market. The **prevailing focus on quantitative dimensions** could also be thwarting progress and business schools may be missing out on the qualitative aspects of sustainability: new perspectives that broaden our understanding of sustainability is needed and can provide many useful insights. On the other hand, **incorporating the key, simple message from climate science to reduce CO2 emissions** would be beneficial in educating sustainability-driven decision-makers: we need to reduce the emissions at all cases and at all times as quick as possible. An excellent example is the [Carbon Literacy Training for Business Schools](#) developed by Petra Molthan-Hill at Nottingham Trent University. **Students are also going to be key drivers of this change**, as they are seeking to develop new conscious solutions, their enthusiasm can be really felt and their role should be reinforced.

*Sustainability is going to happen
because it is actually about survival!*

[RECORDING Fishbowl discussion](#)

Resources for further use

In order to keep up with the objectives of the event, in this section we are sharing some useful resources and materials that our participants, members and any interested stakeholders are encouraged to access and use in their business, research and teaching practices:

- [EMMA Safety Footwear presentation](#)
- [European Venture Philanthropy Association presentation](#)
- NN Investment Partners and Glass Lewis joint study: "[Exploring the links between ESG supervision and performance](#)"
- Opinion piece on business schools and responsible investing: "[Our business schools haven't made the responsible business-finance join yet. They must, and here's how](#)"
- Opinion piece on "[The Social Impact of Business Schools](#)"
- [Carbon Literacy Training for Business Schools](#)

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank our **Steering Committee** that provided us with very useful insights and helped us steer the goals and the programme in the right direction.

Thank you to:

- **Caroline de Moor** - Sustainability Specialist at ING Belgium
- **Joan Fontrodona** - Professor and Director of Business Ethics Department, IESE Business School
- **Judith Verhoeven** - Sustainability Manager, ING Belgium
- **Luk Van Wassenhove** - Emeritus Professor of Technology and Operations Management, INSEAD

Lastly, the event could not have happened without our excellent speakers and all the participants! Thank you!

